

Impact of Transferable Skills on Youth Employability: A Review of Technical and Vocational Education and Training Institutions in Kenya

Koros K. Henry¹ and Nyongesa Regina²

¹Kamukunji Technical and Vocational College P. O. Box 1626-00600, Nairobi

²The Eldoret National Polytechnic P. O. Box 4461-30100, Eldoret

*Corresponding author's Email: h.koros02@gmail.com

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Abstract

Various concepts and approaches in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) have been introduced and implemented, especially the formal education system to bridge and facilitate the acquisition of transferable skills for youth employability. Despite the recognition of the important role that integration of transferable skills plays in transforming TVET, literature on the topic of integration of transferable skills in TVET remains limited. Therefore this review explored evidence-based literature on the integration of transferable skills into the TVET system for youth employability among TVET institutions in Kenya. Secondary data was collected from different sources. These included journal articles, websites, research papers, and other academic publications. The objective of the review was to explore evidence-based literature on the impact of transferable skills on youth employability among TVET institutions in Kenya. The review noted that transferable skills play an important role in enhancing youth employability and that this development should be reflected in TVET. While the extent to which transferable skills are integrated into TVET varies, reference to transferable skills can be found in policy frameworks through its integration into TVET pedagogies, conducive environments establishment and conceptual distinction between TVET and academic education. It was apparent from this review that measurement, assessment and reporting significantly enhance the extent to which transferable skills were meaningfully addressed in the delivery of training. The review concluded that the integration of transferable skills through delivery and assessment practices, allows broader improvements in the quality of teaching and learning that take place in TVET institutions which adequately develop the core skills that can so profoundly enhance the employability of learners and jobseekers. The review recommended that to enhance youth employability, proper clear policies and guidance should be enhanced in the integration and implementation of transferable skills in TVET.

Key words: Integration, Transferable Skills, TVET, Youth Employability

Introduction

Adequate integration of transferrable skills in the Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) system among TVET institutions is necessary for both pre and in-service training (Strietska-Iliina, Chun & Aleksynska, 2021). Skill gaps and mismatches can be associated with an inability to provide the necessary technical and transferable skills needed in the job market (Cappelli, 2015). Therefore, various concepts and approaches in TVET have been introduced and implemented, especially in the formal education system to bridge and facilitate the acquisition of transferable skills for youth employability. Trainees, in addition to basic and specialized knowledge skills, are nowadays expected to have an additional set of skills referred to here as ‘transferable skills that go beyond their occupation. This should not be interpreted as to imply that employability is based solely on these skills but rather that they complement the ‘conventional’ knowledge and skills, thus strengthening individual capacity and employability (OECD, 2013). This review was thus an attempt to explore evidence-based literature on the integration of transferable skills into the TVET system for youth employability among TVET institutions in Kenya.

Developing trainees’ ability to learn is one crucial part of transferable skills, for it can facilitate the transition of youth from learning institutions to work as well as re-entry into education (work-to-learning institution transition). TVET trainees need to learn both inside and outside the workplace and recognize their need for further education and training (UNICEF, 2021). The objective of TVET is to train the workforce in practical skills commensurate to their qualifications. Trainees are expected to be able to demonstrate a sense of ethics and a positive attitude and maintain a professional working style and discipline to become employed/self-employed or pursue further education that meets the national objectives of industrialization and modernization (Raihan, 2014). However, skill gaps and mismatches in TVET systems can be associated with the inability to provide the necessary technical and transferable skills needed in the job market (Cappelli, 2015).

Several practical approaches to teaching transferable skills in TVET range from, at one end, integrating them into separate theoretical subjects to, at the other end, teaching them as partially or fully integrated into practical subjects (Brewer & Comyn, 2015). The extent to which transferable skills are integrated into TVET systems can be found in policy frameworks across the region. In some countries, they have included in-laws and/or regulations, as target goals in policies or as action plans for implementation (Trzmiel, 2014).

Employer surveys indicate that occupation-specific skills are no longer sufficient for workers to meet the needs of national labour markets (OECD, 2013). In a developing country such as Kenya, the estimated unemployment rates reveal the enormity of the labour market challenges because of the large number of youth who are inactive rather than unemployed (Nyerere, 2018). Kenya, like most developing countries, is currently faced with the opportunity and challenge of a 'youth bulge', which could be either a demographic dividend or a disaster (Chatterjee & Ronneberg, 2017). According to the majority of Kenyan employers (12.6%), a lack of technical skills in potential employees is the key factor influencing the skills mismatch problem in Kenya (CAP-YEI, 2017).

Objectives of the study

To explore evidence-based literature on the impact of transferable skills on youth employability among TVET institutions in Kenya.

Methodology

A literature review surveys prior research published in books, scholarly articles, websites, research papers, and any other sources relevant to a particular issue, area of research, or theory, and by so doing, provides a description, summary, and critical evaluation of these works about the research problem being investigated. The purpose was to gain a deep understanding of the current development of the integration of transferable skills in TVET institutions for youth employability. The review process was guided by the key research question that sought to fill the evidence gap by identifying success stories of how TVET institutions have integrated transferable skills in TVET institutions for youth employability.

Literature Review

Theoretical Literature Review

The first mechanism of interest is analogical transfer theory (Gentner, Holyoak, & Kokinov, 2001). Analogical transfer is composed of three subprocesses: retrieving a prior knowledge structure, creating a mapping between it and the current problem or situation, and then using that mapping to generate new knowledge structures relevant to the application context. The transferred knowledge is typically assumed to be a declarative representation, but it can also include procedural attachments (Chen, 2002). However, the evidence also shows that although

people are capable of mapping deep relational structures, the retrieval of an analogue is heavily dependent upon matches between the surface features of the current problem and prior problem solving experiences (Catrambone, 2002).

The second transfer mechanism of interest is knowledge compilation proposed by John R. Anderson and co-workers (Anderson, 1983). Knowledge compilation was specifically proposed to explain how declarative knowledge is brought to bear on problem solving. This mechanism embodies a tradeoff between applicability and efficiency in that it has wide applicability across many contexts but requires a complicated and lengthy application process to translate the declarative knowledge into a set of actions. There is some empirical support for knowledge compilation but the evidence is not extensive (Neves & Anderson, 1981).

The third transfer mechanism of interest is Ohlsson's (1996) error correction mechanism. Proposed that learner identify and correct his or her errors. The constraint violation theory has both declarative and procedural components that operate in parallel, and the function of declarative knowledge is to constrain possible problem solutions. The power of declarative knowledge is that it can help the learner pinpoint the cause of an error, and transfer is the process by which errors are identified and remedied. This mechanism has wide applicability in that the constraints can be applied to a variety of problems that may require different strategies or sequences of actions to produce the correct solution. The constraint violation theory has been shown to generate power law learning curves (Ohlsson, 1996) and to support the design of successful tutoring systems (Mitrovic & Ohlsson, 1999).

Empirical Literature Review

Intergrating transferable skills into TVET curriculum

Nyerere (2018) assessed on technical vocational education and training institutions' curriculum in Kenya: What strategies can position the youth for employment? The study employs the social cognitive career theory perspective to assess Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) institutions' curriculum coverage of various skills in Kenya. The relevance of the curricula to the labour market and barriers affecting institutions' capacity to implement practical-oriented and demand-driven curricula was further examined. A cross-sectional research design was adopted using a mixed-method approach to gather and analyse data. Findings revealed different levels of coverage of soft and technical skills in the curriculum.

Inadequate resources, lack of modern equipment and technology, and minimal adoption of practical components in the curriculum were identified as barriers to acquiring skills, consequently affecting TVET students' capacity to secure employment.

According to Hadiyanto and Ibrahim (2013), trainers should not simply talk and explain what transferable skills are, but they should let trainees experience for themselves the practical application of these skills. They study on students' generic skills at the National University of Malaysia and the National University of Indonesia. Trainers allow trainees to experience for themselves the practical application of generic skills. For example, trainers could apply student-centered learning strategies such as group assignments, presentations and individual assignments as it could help acquire transferable skills. Finding reveals that there is a different but similar trend in students' generic skills practiced at the National University of Malaysia and the National University of Indonesia. Transferable skills should be integrated TVET higher learning institutions as it would guarantee trainees, graduate, with complete skills required by the employers.

Brewer and Comyn (2015) in their research on integrating core work skills into TVET systems: case studies of six countries, assert that there are several practical approaches to training transferable skills in TVET ranging from, at one end, integrating them into separate theoretical subjects, at the other end, teaching them as partially or fully integrated into practical subjects. There is a clear implication that an explicit focus on the delivery and assessment of core skills should be given priority in pre-service and in-service teacher and trainer development programmes. Much remains to be done to ensure that TVET and skills systems adequately develop the core skills that can so profoundly enhance the employability of learners and jobseekers.

Making a conducive learning environment for transferable skills in TVET

According to Ondieki, Kahihu and Muthoni (2019), to promote transferable skills in TVET a conducive learning environment must be enhanced to nurture these skills. Such an environment can only be created through a holistic approach at both national and institutional levels. Using content analysis, the study found that continuous effort to broaden the scope of the transferable skills is necessary if students are to develop skills relevant to the labour market and to ensure their gainful employment after graduation. Trainees should be encouraged to explore and expand these skills inside and outside of school to broaden the scope of the transferable skills

that is integration of transferable skills in the course content should not be restricted to the classroom.

To foster transferable skills, smart choices need to be made concerning the appropriate integration approach (Parisi et al., 2019). Time allocation and group sizes, as well as the availability of public utilities also need to be taken into account. While there is no ‘one-size-fits-all’ approach to making learning spaces adequate for the integration of transferable skills, to prevent unnecessary delays and setbacks, school spaces, facilities and equipment need to be considered before implementing transferable skills training (Brewer & Comyn, 2015).

Ngure (2022) researched on the integration of skills development to a continuous skill acquisition spectrum. One important way of doing this is to seek and create growth within and between individuals through continuous training and development that makes people adapt and interact in functional and constructive ways and the process result in growth in the organizations and society. Behaviorism, Cognitivism and Constructivism models were discussed as they anchor lifelong learning and training. Productivity, employment creation, sustainability, structural changes, domestic growth and social integration were found to be the accrued benefit of skills integration.

Clear lines between TVET and general education of transferable skills at different levels

Rein (2012) study on the blurring distinction between TVET and academic Higher Education (HE) and the prerequisites to create stronger ties between these sectors by improving the chances of permeability and facilitating learning pathways. TVET graduates will have to acquire a holistic competence, whether this is related to work, education, citizenship, personal issues and which is expected to adapt to complex and unpredictable conditions. He found that the creation of stronger ties between different levels generates a new space for TVET’s future by the fusion of academic drift in vocational programs and vocational drift in academic programs, which will reinforce solutions to promote permeability and mobility across education and occupational sectors.

It is assumed that a consequent shift to learning outcomes, addressing compatibly both academic and occupational requirements in the development of qualifications, will make the capability to act across the education and training systems more explicit. Consequently, this will facilitate the visibility of the intersection and compatibility of vocational and higher education approaches. Their research study (Rein & Majumdar, 2018) asserts that in terms of

quality development of qualifications and programs, this might be further promoted by integrated learning outcome concepts based on theory-practice linkages in ‘traditional’ programs as well as in embedded programs that integrate academic and work-based learning in an adapted way e.g. as dual study.

At the tertiary level, the blurring of lines is occurring as a result of the massification of higher academic education which is the outcome of the economic ‘pull’ of higher-level qualifications and the ‘push’ into education from a lack of available jobs. To ensure access, equity and quality of higher education, many education systems have been moving towards ‘institutional differentiation. “Differentiation is described as the process through which new entities in a system emerge” (Gamble, 2013). He found that TVET teachers need to have subject knowledge, need to know how to teach that subject and how to construct a curriculum to replace educational knowledge as ‘generic’ with a stronger understanding of the relation between a particular form of knowledge and its pedagogy.

Making it count: measurement and assessment of transferable skills in TVET

Sheila (2015) review on Co-creating Tools for Measuring Impact of Life Skills on Adolescents: Insights from Scoping Study in East Africa. The study aimed at determining the viability of supporting the co-creation of access Life Skills assessment tool or tools and the willingness of sampled organizations to participate in the process. The study combined a desk review with in-depth interviews. Sixteen civil society organizations were purposively selected from a long list of 63 working in the adolescence and life skills space in Kenya, Tanzania and Uganda. The research found that many organizations have tools to measure and assess life skills but they may not be effective or user-friendly. Also, there is a need for understanding both quantitative and qualitative tools which work best in measuring and assessing life skills in particular contexts. The study concluded that decision-making is the most frequently prioritized life skill for adolescents across the East African region.

TVET trainees are given the training to acquire the knowledge, skills, and attitudes set during their studies. Assessment of trainee competence is essential to confirm that trainees have demonstrated mastery of knowledge and skills and the essential ability required to perform tasks according to specific curriculum standards in TVET (Yunos et al., 2017). The study found that assessment in measuring trainee achievement, especially in skills, is still lacking, especially in TVET. Therefore, it has an impact on the learning outcomes that trainees are

expected to achieve in terms of knowledge, skills, and competencies (Haolader, Ali & Foysol, 2015).

The change in an assessment provides a clear picture of the world of research to determine the assessment that dominates nowadays. The relevant assessment approach in TVET exists in various terminologies, such as competency-based assessment and performance appraisal. This terminology conceptually has the same meaning, yet there are differences between each other in TVET (Yunos et al., 2017). In TVET, performance appraisal is used to measure trainees' competence. Performance appraisal refers to the methods used by teachers to deliver teaching, knowledge, and skills, while competence emphasizes minimum standards by adding levels of criteria, value orientation, and quality of movement (Ab Rahman et al., 2020). Ab Rahman et al., 2020 in the research study found that assessments conducted for various purposes depending on the stakeholders to obtain information that can improve trainees' achievement and improve trainers' training. Therefore, performance appraisal is based on the focus on set objectives and competence is based on criteria.

Conclusions

Reference to transferable skills can be found in policy frameworks through its implementation into TVET pedagogies, conducive environments establishment and conceptual distinction between TVET and academic education. It was apparent from this review that measurement, assessment and reporting significantly enhance the extent to which transferable skills were meaningfully addressed in the delivery of training. These provide the opportunity for broader improvements in the quality of training and learning that take place in TVET institutions which adequately develop the transferable skills that can so profoundly enhance the employability of learners and jobseekers.

There is a need to improve the training of transferable skills to trainees through the core curriculum, particularly in their early career period. Technical skills require transferable skills to unlock the youth so that they can act creatively in a competitive labour market. For transferable skills to be useful to both youth and employers, they need to be tailored to and practiced within actual workforce conditions and market demands. There is emerging agreement that transferable skills play an important role in the workplace and that this development should be reflected in TVET.

Recommendations

Given the evidence adduced from the literature of cases reviewed, the following recommendations were made:

- (a) To facilitate proper integration and implementation, clear policies and guidance on proper integration and implementation of transferable skills in TVET should be enhanced.
- (b) A conducive learning environment can be created through a holistic approach at both national and institutional to nurture transferable skills that need to be made in curriculums and lesson plans.
- (c) Appropriate, context-specific ways of measuring transferable skills need to be developed. Occupation-specific assessment frameworks that allow for context-related adjustments will guide TVET providers in assessing transferable skills.

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